

E-LEARNING AS LEARNING RESOURCES**Miss Kaninde Sambodhi Vitthalrao****Miss Bhosale Prerana Tukaram****Abstract:**

E-learning is just one of the many terms which are used in literature and business about e-learning. E-learning is defined by many people, in many ways, and as it is most important to gain a clear understanding of what e-learning is, we present some definitions and related terminology of the e-learning world.

E-learning comprises all forms of electronically supported learning and teaching. The information and communication systems, whether networked learning or not, serve as specific media to implement the learning process. The term will still most likely be utilized to reference out-of-classroom and in-classroom educational experiences via technology, even as advances continue in regard to devices and curriculum.

Keywords: *E-Learning***Introduction:-**

E-learning is essentially the computer and network-enabled transfer of skills and knowledge. E-learning applications and processes include Web-based learning, computer-based learning, virtual education opportunities and digital collaboration. Content is delivered via the Internet, intranet/extranet, audio or video tape, satellite TV, and CD-ROM. It can be self-paced or instructor-led and includes media in the form of text, image, animation, streaming video and audio.

At the dawn of the 21 st century new dimension education is called E-learning has progressed very fast. In this present research researcher has been focused on E-learning as a learning resource, meaning of E-learning, definition, types of E-learning & educational importance's of E-learning.

Meaning & Definition of E-learning:-

E-learning can be generally defined as a teaching by means of IT. This description is very general and includes various educational activities (self-studying, on-line lectures, discussions and group work on-line) conducted using various technologies and equipment (training in Internet, company intranet, CDs, portable devices etc.). In eLearning, modern technologies are used at every stage of teaching process, from planning and development of training, through its implementation and distribution, to administrating and results evaluation.

E-learning is a new education concept by using the Internet technology, it deliveries the digital content, provides a learner-orient environment for the teachers and students. The e-learning promotes the construction of life-long learning opinions and learning society.

Tom Kelly, Cisco: “E-learning is about information, communication, education and training. Regardless of how trainers categorize training and education, the learner only wants the skills and knowledge to do a better job or to answer the next question from a customer.”

“E-learning provides the potential to provide the right information to the right people at the right times and places using the right medium.”

1. E-learning is a new education concept; it may different from the old educational concept. We should provide a new explanation to this new concept.
2. Delivery of the digital content is the main characters of e-learning. We can tell what is e-learning and what is not.
3. This definition extends the environment on the Internet. We mean that the Internet provides a learning environment for the students and teachers. This environment is learner-oriented, so we can throw out the thoughts of traditionally teacher-center's instruction in classroom.
4. As a new concept of education, e-learning gives a condition for us to realize the life-long learning principle and help us to build a more real learning society.

As a new education system, it has been developed fast in china, But I think the development progress is different from the western countries. The e-learning plays more in high education for the reason of fast need of high education.

Types of e-learning:-

There are different ways to present eLearning. You can simplify your course creation process by identifying up front the best way to present your material.

1 **Traditional eLearning** - highly produced web courses

2 **Rapid eLearning** - quickly produced web courses

3 **There are two types of Rapid eLearning**

4 **Asynchronous** - student directed, self paced learning

5 **Synchronous** - set time (phone/Internet classroom sessions)

Educational Importance Of E-learning:-

1. E-learning is a type of teaching and learning that one can be obtained by the means of online technology. Instead of going to school and attend a regular class.
2. This e-learning is done in the comfort of your own home wherein you can also gain intellectually.
3. This application and procedure consist of online learning, computer support education, virtual and digital teamwork.
4. This is advantageous to those who have less time in going one place to another.
5. Others that have a day job and still want to pursue their studies can benefit from e-learning. He can just learn at home after work at his free time and not thinking of the pressure that he might get late for class.
6. For students it acts as boon in getting knack of easier said than done topics as well as saving time.
7. For teachers e-learning helps in learning the right skill required to teach students.
8. For those who are working and needs to attend trainings, e-learning is also an advantage. You can just have the training at your home via web based learning and other form of high technology education.

9. Many educational institutions nowadays are turning up the web world and teaching students online which has changed the entire spectrum of teaching methods.
10. The importance of e-learning is that it is student centered which focuses on students particular needs.
11. The Education/Tools that e-learning provides surpass all other forms of learning methods. This medium of e-learning has made studying very easy.
12. It simultaneously authorizes learners of different backdrop to equally access the superlative resources, learning and referral materials, tutoring, and teaching sessions from knowledgeable instructors.
13. E-learning is crucial especially for those who are sick and needs to be at home or at the hospital at all times.
14. With this new way of teaching, no student will be left out. All lessons can be learned in just one click. This allows any user to be in a live class of any subject that he wants. No matter where the professor is at that moment, students can still learn by the help of the internet. With this arrangement, students tend to learn easily and they are permitted to download whatever study material they want and need.
15. There is no limitation of time in addition to people can even learn while on move.
16. It is acting as a boon to people who cannot attend classroom lectures to hectic work schedule.
17. . In many institutions and colleges good attendance is the first criterion to sit for exams. The online medium has eliminated all these issues of attendance due to the flexibility of choosing one's own desired time to study online. The online Teaching methods are unique and help in understanding the texts easily.
18. One can study at their own set time and place.
19. E-learning thus has made it easy for people to pursue studies while working. Further the online learning is economical and one learns while they earn. Any one can pursue studies with the online methods of learning. There are no hard and fast rules of learning

through online medium. These are truly convenient and help teachers, students and all other people who use e-learning of education.

20. Many educational institutions are adopting this method of education/tools to make learning fun among students.

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